

Applications Of Global Positioning System in Fisheries

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Introduction

Global Positioning System (GPS) is a satellite-based navigation system determining the accurate position or location of an object on earth's surface. It stands for NAVSTAR GPS (Navigation Satellite Timing and Ranging Global Positioning System). A GPS receiver's job is to locate four or more of these satellites, figure out the distance to each, and use this information to calculate its own location. This operation is based on a simple mathematical principle called triangulation. In a sense it's like giving every square block on the planet a unique address. When people talk about a "GPS", they usually mean a GPS receiver in order to calculate the exact position on earth. GPS receiver measures the signal transit time between the point of observation and four different satellites whose positions are known. Each satellite transmits its exact position and its precise on-board clock time to earth at a frequency 1575.42 MHz. These signals are transmitted at the speed of light (300,000 km/sec) and therefore require approximately 67.3 m/s to reach a position on the earth's surface located directly below the satellites. Further 3.33micro second is required for the signals for each excess kilometer of travel.

GPS is a worldwide radio navigation system formed from a constellation of 24 satellites and their ground stations. It provides continuous three-dimensional positioning 24 hours a day throughout the world. The GPS technology has a tremendous number of applications in Geographic Information System (GIS) data collection, surveying, and mapping. The advent of geospatial information technologies including Remote Sensing (RS), GIS and GPS, individually as well as jointly, are playing a significant role in the development and inclusive growth of the nation.

GPS allows the user to very accurately establish his/her location on the earth's surface. GPS was started under the Department of Defence, USA in 1973.

GPS is a system and has the following three major components:

- i. Satellites
- ii. Ground Control Stations
- iii. GPS receivers or units

Satellites

There are 24 satellites and 3 spare satellites. The exact location of each of the satellites at any given moment is known. Very accurate clocks are installed on-board these satellites. The satellites send radio signals continuously towards earth. These signals contain several pieces of information such as satellite ID number, time stamp, exact position of satellite etc.

Ground control stations

There are five control stations to monitor the satellites. These stations enable information on earth to be transmitted to the satellites. Control stations track satellites and update the position of each satellite continuously. These stations ensure accuracy of the system.

GPS receivers

GPS units are referred to as receivers. These units receive radio signals from satellites, which contain important information such as time stamp, satellite ID number, satellite position etc.

The receiver knows exactly when the signal leaves the satellite (time stamp) and when the signal arrives at the receiver. Hence, it is possible to calculate the distance from satellites as distance is product of time & velocity of light. The receiver also knows the exact position of the satellite via the signal. The receiver is therefore able to determine its exact distance from satellite.

Important applications of GPS in fisheries

- ❖ The potential use of GPS for fisheries and aquaculture is huge. It is a useful tool in providing cost effective data for creation and updating of GIS. Its use is being increasingly made to provide ground control points (GCPs) for remote sensing applications.
- ❖ The latest GPS equipment also includes software which can allow for the capture of any attribute or feature data along with its GPS given position, so as to form a field mapping system. The data obtained can then be directly exported to GIS package.
- ❖ In marine fisheries, it would allow for a survey vessel to continuously monitor water quality along any transect while recording the exact location. The real time mapping of data could then be done. It is also possible to record location of trawlers and also trawler catch data at a specified interval of time and at the end of a fishing trip, the vessel would have a complete record on disk of catch against location

Site surveys: One of the most common reasons for the failure of aquaculture projects and for adverse environmental effects is locating developments on inferior sites. Survey data capture using GPS are very useful in aquaculture site selection. With the development of the geographic information system (GIS) and availability of remote sensing data, it is now possible to select environmentally suitable areas rapidly and systematically. Slope, soil characteristics, vegetation and water supply of aquaculture lands can be pinned accurately and used in both decisions making and farm design.

River mapping: The entire course of a river, streams, lakes can be mapped with useful information as depth, flow direction at each point, width, etc. Species occurrence and abundance maps are also easy to generate on such water bodies using GPS. This makes ecological studies easy.

Species studies: GPS tracking system-based tags can be used to track invasive species, endangered species, fish migrations and population changes. These information on GIS systems can be shared and updated at any time through the use of web-based data management. Using radio and hydro acoustic telemetry, biologists and scientist are able to build up large amount of data on species, which can be used to track patterns of migration, spawning locations and preferred habitat.

Water quality monitoring: GPS could be an invaluable utility tool in water quality monitoring. In South-East Asia, GPS has been used in surveys to determine the impact of tsunami on aquaculture.

Fish Ecology: Developments in sensor-controller Technology, computers and position systems now bring new opportunities for farm management and aquaculture. GIS analysis of fish habitat has become more sophisticated often combining numerical or statistical models of fish abundance, growth and prey availability with the physical characteristics of the habitat in a GIS framework Updated maps provide watershed managers with the tools they need to effectively monitor water quality. GPS data capture generates geo-database with the capability to provide decision makers and managers with information on tools for analyzing key decision criteria that support

Selection of sites suitable for different types of aquaculture: Marine, coastal and inland fish farming and eliminate areas unsuitable for aquaculture. GPS based data can help governments and licensing agencies to allocate and approve the appropriate aquaculture projects and guide investors to aquaculture potentials in a state, country or region.

Other application of GPS in fisheries: Other Application include Disease and pest mapping, fisheries and aquaculture infrastructure enumeration and satellite-based navigation systems in capture fisheries. GPS technology helps with traffic routing, underwater surveying, navigational hazard location, and integrated mapping. Fishing fleets are able to navigate to fishing locations, digitally and easily mark specific locations (docks, fishing hotspots, boat drifts, trolling paths, and more) and track fish migrations with ease using GPS aided fish finder devises.

Conclusion

Global positioning system has revolutionized positioning concepts, though it started primarily as a navigation system for the military. Today the global GPS has become an international utility. In addition to its ease of use, and worldwide all-weather operation, GPS owes its popularity to the dependable high accuracy with which positions, time and direction can be determined. As a tool of precision agriculture, GPS satellites broadcast signals that allow GPS receivers to calculate their position. This information is provided in real time, meaning that continuous position information is provided while in motion. Having precise location information

at any time allows crops, soils and water measurements to be mapped. GPS receivers, either carried to the field or mounted on implements allow users to return to specific locations to sample or treat those areas.

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